

STUDY ON THE
ESTABLISHMENT OF
CONFORMANCE TESTING LABS
IN GREECE
IN THE AREAS OF IT & T

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY
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BY

N. MALAGARDIS

A. CULLEN

B. KIRSCH

A. KOFINAS

E.N. PROTONOTARIOS

E. SPITHAS

C. TAPINOS

J. TENCKHOFF

N. VERNARDAKIS

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Importance of OSI

The development of the unified IT & T market in the Community by 1992 requires the full interoperability of equipment in a multivendor competitive environment. The European development of OSI must be employed to its full potential as an instrument to open up the IT & T market and establish a competitive environment necessary for the introduction of European innovative products.

In order to allow for interoperability of heterogeneous systems in the domains of telematics and business communication, offering the same services (document handling, message exchange, etc.), it is necessary, beyond the existence of protocol standards, that these protocols be correctly set up in networks with interconnected equipment. It is also necessary to have access to specialized services allowing the control of properly setting up of these standardized communication protocols.

Testing conformance to standards will enhance the quality of products and services in the Community. We see a growing user involvement for policy formation in the computer and Telecommunication industry.

During the last few years, certification has soared as a major problem, which has to be faced, through the European Community. The development of technical tools, through international cooperation, has been stimulated through specific programs. CTS is one characteristic example of coordinated effort through the CEC stimulus and guidance.

1.2 The Development of CTS

It is well known that standards in computing and telecommunications suffer from the exponential nature of technology growth in these areas and its inherent complexity. The ways of making up a standard have been established at the beginning of the industrial era, but they are more suitable to mechanical applications which require precise physical as opposed to functional descriptions, containing the embedded intellectual investment. Computer technology is differentiated in that it takes consideration of the contents as well as of the forms of the objects it manipulates adding thus to the difficulty of expressing a standard in a rigid form.

Another reason is the reluctance of users and manufacturers to adopt standards and use them in marketing new products. This leads to a particularly sensitive point in the promotion of standards. A standard is without any basis, if there is no way to check on its conformity and to validate products against it certification.

Certification is a mechanism enabling the promotion of standards; it may be considered as an accompanying and indispensable activity to their consolidation and use. Today's standards, even the so called "de facto" standards, have the possibility of being checked and certified. The value of Certification is enhanced by the confidence that the different parties involved should have towards the organization performing this operation. This confidence must be founded on regulations and, for certain cases, on legislation stipulating the relationships between vendors, their clients and the Certification Center.

Given the above, the necessity for the present study arose from the experience gained by the work implemented through CTS-1 and CTS-2 programmes.

One of the most striking aspects of these programmes was that the involvement of the less technically developed countries of CEC was very low if non existent.

1.3 The Study of CTS in Greece

Since Greece was a representative case of the above, a decision was taken by the CEC DGXIII to study the situation in Greece and investigate what was necessary to be done for this country and which measures could be taken in order for Greece to play an active part in the European CTS programmes.

The overall philosophy for achieving the above scope, was not only based on determining the conditions under which CTS services could be established in Greece and which sectors were viable but also what segments for CTS development are appropriate according to the needs for technology transfer to Greece. So the study addresses the topic from more than one aspect and goes beyond the arid investigation of various themes and their economic justification for Greece.

In order for Greece to catch up to the emerging new technologies and especially to implement OSI services, the country has to develop all components of the necessary environment. CT Services belong undoubtedly to this environment.

Certification and validation have a limited existence and tradition in this country and further they do not extend into modern technologies and in particular to IT & T areas. The main idea is to investigate and use the existing potentials and funnel them in those areas where economic justification is realistic and in those where technology transfer seems necessary.

The experts participating in this study, believe that the implementation of such services in Greece beyond the fact that they will allow interoperability between systems they will also allow the enhancement of quality in local made applications. Above all, however, it will help IT & T standards penetrate the market and people to understand and use them.

The proposed structures described in chapter 2 of the third report materialize response to the needs described afore. The main target being to give Greece its share of the European IT & T renaissance and raise its technical capacity to the common standards. At the same time benefit comes from interoperability achieved through cooperating compatible parts of a European production mechanism

In addition, Greece will benefit by CT services not only for the proper development of its IT & T industry but mainly for insuring intelligent procurement of hardware and software in its public and private sectors within the unified European market.

Being incorporated in the European market, Greece has to be equipped with tools of the same caliber and quality. Conformance Testing Services is one of these tools.

Since Conformance Testing is not yet a lucrative occupation, the setting up will need substantial help from the public sector in credit, market encapture and finance. So it might seem at first as a too ambitious idea if we don't consider the absolute necessity for those who are in the market already. There is a sector though where a specialty may be picked up. This is the character set definition and testing.

Any way CTS labs in Greece have to be selected from areas of new technology which will help knowledge to be boosted and allow engineers to enter the IT & T new age.

The proposed structure tries to unite the newly existing certification scheme with the possibilities of certification services complemented by consultancy for the users in the domain of IT & T standards applications.

1.4 Outline of the Study Report

The "Study on the Establishment of CTS in Greece in the Areas of IT & T" is presented in three separate reports.

In the first report the Community policy on IT & T Standardization, Certification and Conformance Testing is covered as well as the existing situation and policy in Greece on the above matters. A short description of the relevant subprogrammes of the Greek IMP and STAR programme is given. The Greek participation in CEC/CTS programme is briefly reviewed. In the second chapter, the information capture methodology is described. In the third chapter, the visit reports to Greek laboratories, companies and unions are presented. In chapter IV and V, the user requirements and the infrastructure of Greek Telecommunications are covered. The second part of the first report presents an early reference model for CTS in Greece.

In the second report economic considerations and the dynamics of the CTS industry are developed in Chapter 2. The analysis presented in this chapter, are preliminary and tentative, but, if correct, have powerful implications as regards recommendations for policy in the CT domain. Policy questions and scenarios of development are analyzed in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 contains the European experience on CTS based on the team's visits to the European Laboratories. The CT Services provided in Europe, as well as the structure of representative European CTS Laboratories (FTZ and GMD in Germany, CNET in France and CSELT in Italy) are described in some detail. Subcontractors' activities are mentioned separately because of their special role and impact. Technology transfer is covered in Chapter 5. Not only existing, but also planned and possible future technical domains are examined. The final Chapter contains the identification of IT & T areas suitable for conformance testing in Greece. Criteria of selection and grading of the priorities are included. Brief descriptions of the relevant services as well as conformance to EEC regulations are given.

The third report contains the USA experience. The structure and scope of COS and NIST are described and conclusions concerning the market trends and the policy procedures of the CTS in USA are made. Criteria of competence for setting up Certification Labs in Greece are covered in Chapter 2. The organizational structure of the IT and T CTS in Greece is proposed. Managerial and educational aspects are examined and infrastructural requirements per testing area are analyzed. The National Accreditation System is described in Chapter 3. Technical and economical recommendations are covered in the same chapter. Financial aspects are presented in last chapter.

1.5 The Executive Summary

This Executive Summary synthesizes the principal results and conclusions. In the following Section (2.0), the main Recommendations are stated at-a-glance for ease of reference. They are supplemented by a comprehensive Recommendation set in Section 5. Close attention to this latter Section is strongly advised if the reader wishes to understand the integrity of the package of recommendations as a whole. The technical findings and conclusions are found in Section 3; in particular, the selected technical areas are detailed in 3.5. An attempt has been made to minimize duplication with projects underway elsewhere in the EC yet maximize the potential benefits for Greece arising from entry into the CT domain. As a latecomer, and with limited resources available, fulfilling this aim was not without problems since Greece's technology transfer needs in IT&T generally are substantial.

Section 4 presents the economic analysis and conclusions. Cost-benefit analysis was considered an inappropriate tool to assess the complexity of this newly-emerging area. Monetary measures of viability or consumers' surplus cannot grasp the strategic issues which became the focal point of the analysis. As Section 4 explains, unexpected findings have occurred which have distinct implications both for the recommended implementation strategy in Greece and the likely requirements of future policy at the European level.

In short, both the technical and economic work performed for this Study have recognized the need to achieve a balanced and realistic portfolio of priorities, actions, and instruments which, while exploiting the opportunities presented through the leading role of the EC, also provide an effective and sustainable local framework designed to contribute to the rapid improvement of Greek IT&T resources. This has meant, in practical terms, finding the optimal balance of functions and responsibilities as between private and public sector involvement.

In conclusion, we would like to emphasize that the task ahead is a difficult one. The difficulties are both objective and subjective. Objective in the sense that the barriers and constraints pertaining to IT&T development and use in Greece are immense. Subjective in the sense that there is a terrible weight of inertia holding back development because of continued lack of understanding of the benefits of IT&T in general and standards for open systems in particular. If there is to be a more rapid uptake and use of open systems IT&T in Greece, then it is an urgent requirement that there be a transformation of attitudes and behavior amongst decision-makers and investors in Greek industry, commerce, banking, administration and services.

With these imperatives in mind, we express the hope that our recommendations will be not only widely read but also acted upon as a whole since they form an integrated package explicitly designed to contribute to tackling in parallel both the objective and the subjective components of the problem facing diffusion and innovation of IT&T in Greece.

2. MAIN RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations of the study are guided by three basic considerations:

- o The Conformance Testing Laboratories in Greece should be part of the European CTS structure. As a consequence, it should influence and be influenced by the developments in CT work that are taking place throughout Europe, and indeed throughout the world.
- o The Conformance Testing Laboratories in Greece should also function as an instrument for the development of Greek IT & T industry. This implies that they should be involved in development work.
- o The Conformance Testing Laboratories should help large firms and the public sector to function in a multivendor environment. It will accomplish its function by providing the necessary facilities and advice for intelligent procurement.

2.1 General Recommendations

The general recommendations are the following:

1. Adopt, as quickly as possible, the European Certification and Standardization policy as detailed in the 2nd and 3rd Interim Report.
2. Set up, as quickly as possible, a simple mechanism to guide greek users to obtain testing services from existing Greek or European Laboratories. This is an important consulting function which the laboratory will continue to provide to Greek Industry and public administration.
3. Organize a campaign - enterprise networking event - which will give wide publicity to the services available, will demonstrate the commercial importance of standards in the developing single European market.
4. Develop, in collaboration with the relevant Ministry, a GOSIP manual, and prepare model contracts and model calls for bid, in public procurement.

5. Make use of the funds available within the IMP on Informatics and use own matching funds, both in kind in the form of existing laboratory infrastructure and in funds from public investments.
6. Increase Greek involvement in the CEC CTS programme.
7. Specific recommendations concerning ELOT are made in the study.

2.2 Specific Recommendations

Taking into account the whole study and the above considerations we can make the following specific recommendations:

- * A new public sector non-profit body, IPPEYS, should be created. IPPEYS will have two high-level functions: consulting on strategic planning of the public sector's needs in IT&T; and support the implementation in Greece of Council Decision 87/95 by developing its own certification testing facilities.
- * A new private sector firm should be created to specialize in IT&T test tool/suite development and the provision of specialist IT&T standards and software product development consultancy services. The owners of this company should be the representatives of Greek industry, commerce, finance, administration and other services.
- * In the telecommunications sector, there are already existing developments and services available within the CTS Programme. However, for the purposes of National needs OTE should undertake testing of OSI lower layers (public domain). For the future, OTE should investigate the possibility of entering the CTS consortium currently developing a test tool for ISDN basic access.
- * To strengthen Greek participation in the specialist work of test tool development IPPEYS and the new private sector firm should jointly put in applications under the forthcoming CTS-2bis Call for Proposals.
- * In addition to conformance testing, there are complementary testing activities which could be expanded building upon the existing resources of KEPHY.

3. TECHNICAL FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

3.1 Introduction

Being incorporated in the European market, Greece has to be equipped with tools of the same caliber and quality. Conformance Testing Services is one of these tools.

Since Conformance Testing is not yet a lucrative occupation, the setting up will need a serious help from the public sector in credit, market encapture and finance. So it might seem at first as too ambitious idea for those who do not see the absolute necessity for those who are in the market already. There is a sector though where a speciality may be picked up. This is the character set definition and testing.

Any way CTS labs in Greece have to be selected from areas of new technology which will help knowledge to be boosted and allow technicians to enter the IT & T new age.

The proposed structure tries to unite the newly existing certification scheme with the possibilities of certification services complemented by consultancy for the users in the domain of IT & T standards applications.

3.2 Greek Resources and Needs

A major task of the study was to analyze the possibilities of existing testing laboratories in Greece.

Through the extensive visits to various public and private testing services, it became apparent that only a few are currently at a level to contribute to CTS. The most important are:

- o Telecommunications Administration (OTE)
Laboratory for type approval of terminals
- o Hellenic Aerospace Industry (EAB)
Callibration Laboratory
- o Quality Control Centre for Electronic Materials (KEPHY)
Laboratories for Environmental Testing
Laboratory for EMC Testing

Another task was to understand the technical and economic possibilities of Greek industry as well as their future plans and needs for CT services. A full description of the results is formed in the 1st report. Hereby, we are just stressing some of the most important conclusions:

- o An uprising sector in Greece is the software companies

- o The hardware sector in Greece is mainly working in the assembly of IT & T products
- o The software Quality Assurance - CTS is a real need for Greek software industry
- o In addition to CTS, incoming inspection establishments seem of much importance to Greek hardware industry.
- o Tests for interoperability are of vital importance for intelligent procurement by the public sector and by industry.

3.3 Europe: State of the Art

The Study Team visited all the European test laboratories participating in CTS-1 and in all instances requested from the organizations concerned details of their costs, of the prices charged for conformance testing services, and of their current and expected future revenues and profits earned from this source.

Most of the organizations providing testing services stated openly that they were not making profits from them at the present time. Some of the respondents (mainly labs belonging to public sector organizations) stated too that they did not expect to do so in the future either; the key reason identified for this being the high fixed costs associated with providing laboratory facilities as well as the high investment costs involved in purchasing the new test tools and suites.

Other labs, while admitting current losses, nevertheless adopted a more optimistic stance with regard to future revenue prospects. Where this optimism was found in labs belonging to the PTTs, the main ground for optimism usually rested on the view that in-house demand (charged at commercial rates) would eventually repay and justify the costs incurred.

Nearly all the labs are geared-up, with varying degrees of commitment, to offering additional services complementary to conformance testing. Frequently, these extra activities were cited as supplementary sources of revenue.

Indeed, taking into account the cost to a product developer of having his product undergo a full conformance test, some of the labs are consciously emphasizing a consultancy-based approach to service provision. That is, encouraging product developers to make use of the labs' expertise and judgment

on a continuing basis while the product itself is in the design and prototype phases. This, in order to incorporate 'best practice' design into the product from the outset, and thereby maximize avoidance of errors in the software and increase chances that the final product implemented will conform to the standard and pass the test.

Views on the relative importance of revenues earned from this kind of consultancy vary. Providing alternatives to full conformance testing was usually perceived to be particularly important for small- and medium -sized enterprises. More generally, it was felt to make the marketing of conformance testing itself more attractive or palatable. None of these statements should distract us however from the fundamental point: the unprofitability of the labs, whatever their organizational features and range of commercial services.

There will be definite, possibly quite short, demand life-cycles for test services in particular technical areas. The labs appear to be only vaguely aware of this circumstance. This is plain to see in the fact that, in most cases, minimal attention has so far been paid to actively marketing and selling.

It is revealing in this connection that no laboratory was able to provide a business plan or any other form of quantitative estimate to support their assertions about viability prospects. The study team has concluded that this stems (with perhaps two exceptions) not from a desire to protect commercial secrecy but simply, in the majority of cases, from the non-existence of such business plans. Viability, in other words, has not been a cornerstone in the arguments supporting the setting-up of European conformance testing laboratories. Neither is it a prime motivation on the part of the labs : in general, they belong to organizations which appear willing to accept losses from providing these services.

3.4 The US Experience

Certification of software has a long experience in the USA. Since the early seventies the federal government has adopted a procurement policy based on certified products.

The field where certified procurement is most active and successful is the compiler certification. Initiated by the Federal Compiler Test Center then by the Federal Software Test Center and now by the National Institute of Standards and Technology. The emergence of OSI gave a new thrust in validation of IT & T standards so new needs were growing up and simultaneously they were addressing a new and by far larger public.

The National Bureau of Standards has been reshaped and renamed as National Institute for Standards and Technology. An industrial Corporation for Open Systems has been formed in order to perform, among other things, certification and validation of protocols (Corporation for Open Systems -COS).

The new landscape in the USA shows the will to enter the certification area for IT & T standards in the public sector as well in the private sector to control thus the standards evolution on a worldwide basis. Although it is not clear that test suites which will be approved by them will dominate the "certification test suites market", since they will be backed by the worlds biggest customer (US federal government) and the world's biggest companies in IT & T.

At the present time as the report shows it does not seem that this very expensive area is a profit making activity per se but the strategic importance of the whole complex body: standards plus their conformity is recognized by everybody and the expenses attached are not considered as a loss.

From the visit to both the National Institute of Standards and Technology and COS, it was concluded that the Americans consider the CTS programme of the CEC as the key driving force in Europe for the development of Certification and Conformance Testing.

What is of interest for this study is not to repeat the "american paradigm" but using its brief analysis to gain additional insight into the European experience in the light of the U.S. experience. We have argued in the report that the CEC is at the heart of the whole edifice of European Conformance Testing, that is we have a centralized system. Comparison of the European system versus the U.S. system is not a comparison between centralized against a decentralized system, for the simple reason that the U.S. presents both. So our comparison boils down to comparing a centralized system to a system that is both centralized and decentralized at the same time. In the European system the major decisions at the policy level as well as the target level are decided at the centre, which through the local PTTs are implemented in the regions. Interregional divergences as to the scope and utility of Conformance Testing and to some extent local needs account for the duplication in some instances in services provided, in essence a small token of economic inefficiency in exchange for fairness to the regions. The centre is enlightened and knows best. It is moving ahead of its own industry which is weak and slow by international standards, and thus provides for this industry's future targets and goals but at the same time makes Conformance Testing an unprofitable business, since the market is expected to follow. In a way it is ahead of its time and attempts to pull industry in its wake.

3.5 Selection of Technical Areas

Taking into account the results of our visits and interviews and technology transfer aspects, we grouped the criteria for identifying IT & T areas suitable for Conformance Testing in Greece as follows:

- I. Strategic criteria
- II. Development of relevant industries
- III. Economic considerations
- IV. Viability of the laboratories

In order to give grades to the above four figures of merit, a further break up to easily gradable criteria was used. These criteria are neither totally uncorrelated with each other, nor exclusively belong to any of the four generic functions mentioned above. Thus, the selection criteria are:

1. Present and future needs of the Greek industry
2. Impact of CTS on the Greek economy
3. Procurement needs
4. Modernization of the public sector
5. Needs of OTE
6. Impact on the level of technology
7. Availability of expertise in Greece
8. Relevance to Greek Standardization Policy
9. Technology transfer
10. Allignment with the European environment
11. Use of existing relevant laboratories
12. Employment effects
13. Substitution effects
14. Investment multiplication effects
15. Profitability of laboratories

The following table lists the needs of Greece and the services supplied by European laboratories.

TOPICS	Greek needs	European Supplied Services	NOTES
1. 3X, X25, X75	C+E	A+B+C+D+E	Infrastructure peculiarities
2. LAN	B	A+B	Technology Transfer
3. X400	C	B	Technology Transfer
4. FTAM RJE OSIGL VT	B	B	Cooperation with other E labs
5. E Fund transfer (Security)	C Banking		
6. EDIFACT	C		
7. ODA	B		
8. Desk Top Publishing	B+C+D		Testing for Greek Language
9. Reliability Testing Lab	A+D		
10. ISDN	C	B	Cooperation for future actions
11. MAP	D+C	A	Industrial Framework
12. CIM	D+C		Industrial Framework
13. Coded character set	A+B+D+E		
14. EMC	A+D+E		EEC Directive
15. SQA	A+E		Request by Greek industry
16. Modem V-series	C+D+E	Only V32	Request by PTT as absolute Necessity

A : Issuing a Certificate,
C : Interoperability testing,
E : Type Approval

B : CT Formal Services
D : Consulting Services

Table of priorities for the Greek Conformance Testing needs.

4. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS & CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Introduction

The European Community's policies in IT&T and for the completion of the Internal Market by 1992 set the framework within which the economic analysis was conducted. Their main relevant features for this study are:

- promotion of, and support for, open systems standards in IT&T and hence of a competitive, multivendor market;
- promotion of, and support for, the establishment of IT&T conformance testing laboratories providing 3rd party test services;
- mutual recognition of accredited laboratories' test reports;
- liberalization of IT&T equipment and services markets (e.g.. Green Paper on Telecommunications);
- promotion of public sector purchasing of OSI-based systems via Council Decision 87/95.

The Study Team has taken these elements of the EC's policy framework as their point of departure. They have not felt it necessary to contradict the validity of the CEC's policies. On the contrary, the CEC's initiatives in this field have been firmly integrated into the overall analysis and it is shown how the European developments in conformance testing are primarily a function of the CEC's leadership over the market.

Although referred to in the original terms of reference, the Study Team were unable to proceed with a cost-benefit analysis methodology. An initial assessment of the economic and other factors involved showed that this was inappropriate. Furthermore, the nature of the data and evidence available was not conducive to this kind of approach.

Nevertheless, the economic analysis has arrived at important and unexpected results (4.1 & 4.2). In short, despite the fact that conformance testing itself is probably not a viable business, there are several related and complementary activities which can be. Moreover, these activities are of strategic significance for the future health and productivity of the Greek economy as a whole.

Several important general conclusions arise from the results of the economic analysis. These are described below (4.4). However, with a view to maximizing the realism of the recommendations deriving from them, the specific conditions and constraints imposed both by local Greek conditions and by the already-existing European-level developments have been taken into account (4.3).

4.2 The European Experience

The Study Team visited several of the European organizations involved in the EC's CTS Programme to gather information about developments at the European level. The quality of financial and business information provided by these encounters was uneven. Nobody was willing to divulge detailed cost data and not one Organization admitted to having a business plan.

Nevertheless, in all cases, it was clear that none of the laboratories offering CT services were profitable. A number of reasons were given explaining these organizations' involvement despite the absence of profitability. These were:

- profits are expected at some future date as demand evolves
- complementary consultancy services (helping clients at the product design and development stage) are expected to provide the main revenue source
- laboratory testing has high fixed costs and can never be viable; testing is however a necessary function and the consequent costs are therefore an inevitable overhead;
- having access to test "know-how" is strategically important to remaining competitive as it helps stay abreast of technology developments

Thus, while the provision of CT services defies any narrowly-defined profit and loss criteria, other techno-economic and strategic reasons exist explaining these organizations' involvement.

On further investigation, the economic analysis uncovered an unexpected but crucial further dimension to the CT area. In order to provide 3rd party testing services the laboratories have had to invest in the development of sophisticated test tools and suites. Almost without exception, they have

achieved this by awarding funded subcontracts to specialist software houses. This decision to subcontract rested mainly on their need to control costs and also their own relative lack of expertise and lack of suitably-experienced personnel.

In contrast to the non-viable nature of CT services, this software development activity is profitable. Furthermore, the companies involved are in clear contrast to their (mainly PTT) clients. They are usually small, private sector firms whose highly-qualified software engineers are involved in the working groups of the international standardization bodies. Managements are usually young and flexible while Organization and methods are lightweight rather than bureaucratic.

Additionally, and connected to the discovery of this PTT-specialist software house relationship, two other key dynamic processes were uncovered. First, the increasing interconnection of the international standards-setting process with innovation in the domain of advanced software products: the formal methods and tools being used nowadays to create new software products are at the same time the basis for designing the means for testing their implementation. Thus, to be at the leading-edge of innovation in software means also to understand and be involved in the standards-setting game. Second, there exist not one but two relevant product life cycles: the demand for 3rd party CT services and the demand for CT tools and suites. Each of these have their respective determinants but both are likely to be relatively short-lived given the pace of technological change in the sector.

From a policy perspective all three of these findings have strategic implications. The PTT-specialist software house relation highlights on the one hand the requirement for continued support from the EC and on the other the relative weakness of the PTTs in the domain of innovation/diffusion. The increasing integration between standards-setting and advanced software development underlines the potentially strategic role that innovation policy can play. While the brief duration of the product life-cycles indicates that viability in the context of rapidly-changing technology is largely a function of being and remaining first. Since demand pull rather than technology push will increasingly determine the scope of future technical domains and hence the demand for next generations of test tools, suites and services, a focus on the upper layers of the OSI model for future initiatives is advised since it is here that innovation and user interest is highest.

4.3 Europe in the Light of American Developments

In the 1990s the world market for IT&T systems and services will be predominantly based around open systems. It was important therefore to assess Europe's current and likely future position in comparison to that of the USA. The following insights were gained from this analysis:

- the US scheme in contrast to Europe's, is both centralized (COS & NIST) and decentralized (fuller development of market forces) at the same time; this provides for much more demand-oriented feedback to the centre to support priority-setting and the innovation process;
- the RBOCs, the nearest US equivalent of the European PTTs, do not play an important role in this scheme; rather, much greater weight is given to the involvement of large IT user organizations;
- a software sector comprised of small but rapidly-growing firms specializing in tool and protocol analyzer development also exists in the US. However, this sector survives directly from market-led demand not from public sector funding;
- the scope of what is being tested differs: in the US there is much more interest in MAP/TOP than in Europe;
- the Federal authorities seem to be actively pursuing their open systems public procurement policy whereas in Europe there exists only Council Decision 87/95.

All of these divergences and differences of emphasis between the US and Europe suggest important lessons if Europe is to stay ahead in the CTS domain. In the absence of both a CTS-3 and of structural reforms to the prevailing system it is concluded that Europe will be unable to maintain its lead. This undoubtedly has implications for the degrees of freedom of action available to a latecomer such as Greece given the highly centralized construction of the European system.

4.4 System Constraints

On the basis of the foregoing economic analysis and findings a first step in the derivation of recommendations is to specify the general features of the European experience which ideally need to be reproduced in Greece. This approach is justified on the grounds that the CT domain in Europe is led from the centre so the degrees of freedom

available to a latecomer - especially a relatively less-developed latecomer - are very limited. The second step is then to identify the modifications needed to these general requirements in order to take into account the specificities of the Greek socio-economic and technological contexts.

To reproduce the conditions found elsewhere in Europe in Greece will require:

- the continuation of the leading (policy and financing) role of the EC and 'benign centralization': introduction of a CTS-3 or its equivalent;
- the creation of the same PTT-specialist software house subcontractor relation for test tool/suite development;
- recognition of, and rapid policy response to, the changing scope of CT technical domains brings new opportunities;
- exploiting these changes in scope as new niche market opportunities for "leap-frogging" competitors (= innovation policy aspect)

To reveal whether or to what extent these general features can be reproduced in the Greek context and what additional requirements are necessary, the economic analysis highlighted the following conditions and constraints:

- there is both low absolute and relative (to Europe) use of IT&T in Greece; moreover the relative use trend is worsening;
- OTE, the Greek PTT, exhibits poor performance relative to other European PTTs;
- although Greek software houses are one of the relatively more promising parts of the (very weak) indigenous IT&T sector, their products are focused mainly on imitative pc software, rather than advanced applications (another indicator of the underdeveloped character of demand);
- the Greek public sector is at one and the same time an opportunity and a constraint: because of the breadth of state involvement in the national economy it is potentially the major local market segment for OSI products. Yet, it is also slow-moving and inefficient and as such presents obstacles in the way of effective, timely and innovative policy implementation in the IT&T standards, public purchasing and CT domains.

- given the availability of limited financial resources and the need to avoid unnecessary duplication within the EC's CTS Programme, a latecomer such as Greece must put especially her efforts into participating in future actions.

Given these system constraints a number of amendments to the original schema suggest themselves. First, a relative priority must be given to an *accelerated diffusion of IT&T applications* in Greece conforming to open systems standards. This constitutes an essential element in any attempt to reduce the relative backwardness of Greece in IT&T. One component of policy should therefore be the allocation of more resources to raising awareness amongst potential users both of the benefits of implementing current IT&T applications within their organizations and of best practices. Our recommendations include specific and preferred instruments for achieving this goal.

Second, given the stage of development of telecommunications in Greece and in particular the revealed priorities of OTE in its newly-published 1989-92 investment plan, it is inappropriate to attempt to simulate with OTE the PTT-specialist software house relation in the same way that has occurred with some of the larger European PTTs. Nevertheless, our recommendations strongly support the introduction of a surrogate process.

Third, a strong (=independent, technically competent and with effective powers) efficient public sector Organization responsible, inter alia, for policing all public purchasing of IT&T systems is essential if Council Decision 87/95 is to be effectively and universally implemented in Greece.

4.5 Conclusions

In the light of the previous analysis, the following concluding points have emerged:

- o Greece must 'get started' or lose further ground;
- o Test tool development and testing are strategically important for economic development and state of advance in IT&T;
- o Accelerated diffusion of technologies and techniques is necessary;
- o Consultancy and test tool/suite development maybe a profitable activity;
- o Information diffusion needs open environment.

5. CTS IN GREECE

5.1 Main goals of CTS in Greece

According to the deliberations of the study, the main purposes of CTS in Greece should be:

To Support Public Procurement in the country

Public procurement is now governed by Directive 87/95. That is conformance to standards should be an important part for all procurement tenders. Especially where IT & T products are expected to support complex standard specifications the conformance testing may be required in order to reduce risks and raise confidence in these products. Public authorities as major users of IT & T operating wide ranges of data processing systems, office automation facilities and telecommunications networks need "profiles" that is a selection of specific standards among the panoply of existing ones.

Government OSI profiles, GOSIP, have been designed by the UK and the US governments. There is a need for such actions in Greece for the creation of a healthy market environment.

To achieve interoperability of IT & T products

It has become clear that the ability of computer and communications products to be linked and interoperate with a universally accessible global telecommunications network is a basic prerequisite in the emerging european and global economy. So there is a need to support the Open Networking of computer and communications products and services. The customers should be given the flexibility to combine new and existing equipment. This way we reduce dependency on single vendor offerings and ensure that the users will not be locked into one manufacturer's computers, modems and switches. At the same time the user will be able to communicate in computer environments both within and outside their own organization.

To promote standards awareness through information dissemination and consulting.

There is a great need for better understanding of networking opportunities. CTS should offer users a chance to acquire that understanding. These services should provide technical support to government and industry, in the effective safe and economical use of computers and telecommunications, for improving productivity and competitiveness in the international market.

As a result greater responsiveness of vendors and greater customer control will take place. An important factor is to select among existing standards, for testing, a small number that will support user applications in many industries.

5.2 Technical Areas

5.2.1 Approach, Priorities & Criteria

The fundamental principle of avoiding duplication of effort with other European projects, the limited availability of resources, and the wide-ranging needs of the Greek economy have all been taken into account in defining priorities. The recommendations as to the selected technical areas therefore operate at a number of different levels, with differing resource requirements. There are recommendations concerning 3rd Party CTS for IT systems (5.2.3). There are separate recommendations for telecommunications where 1st Party testing only is proposed (5.2.4). Other existing miscellaneous and complementary technical areas (5.2.7 and 5.2.8) may also offer test services opportunities.

Given the importance of realizing accelerated diffusion of technology and know-how, the recommendations give particular emphasis to the need for additional measures - notably, consultancy services (5.2.2) and test tool development (5.2.6) - to support and consolidate the actions in establishing CTS. Finally, with an eye on the changing technical scope of the CT domain, there are also recommendations about second stage (1990-92) developments (5.2.9).

5.2.2 Consultancy Services

The emphasis of available resources and the main priority for the new private company should be on providing *consultancy services*. This will provide a means for realizing technology and know-how transfer both to the local software industry and to users (in particular to the public sector). The dominating presence of users' organizations on the Board of the company will secure both that the company has a client base and that it provides services in line with actual needs.

The focus of consultancy should be on those technical areas which have maximum productivity benefits for users. User organizations are interested primarily in applications which means concentrating on consultancy for the upper

layers of OSI. This suggests focusing on FTAM, MHS and ODA/ODIF/SGML/EDI (=Desk Top Publishing) in the office automation sector. For automation in the finance and banking sector, developments in EFTPOS, in electronic payments cards and in the research being conducted under the Services Integration Applications Pilots (Workplan Tasks 651/652/653) of the EC's RACE Programme should be monitored and results fed to users.

5.2.3 3rd Party Conformance Test Services

OSI Upper Layers

In the start-up phase, there is no need to get involved either in providing test services or in developing test tools. However, the Board of Directors should make business decisions within 6 months whether, and if so what, domains they wish to involve themselves in. The technical domains that the Board should be encouraged to consider as early candidates are mainly those relating to the upper layers of OSI.

LANs (Private Domain)

Penetration of advanced distributed applications requires networking. Greek organizations are far behind. This suggests that LANs (private domain) are a major priority as concerns technology transfer. Given that LAN technology and market share is dominated by US companies and that therefore a sudden increase of domestic demand for LANs would impact negatively the already negative IT trade balance we recommend that ELSYP gives priority to setting-up a joint venture with a major vendor of OSI-compatible LANs.

It should therefore also give priority to offering both testing and consultancy services for private domain LANs. Licenses for existing LAN test tools can be bought. Greece's current participation in the Eureka project COSINE, which is implementing OSI standards in local area networking for the academic research community, should be examined.

5.2.4 Telecommunications

There has been strong participation of PTTs (the CTS-WAN grouping) in the development of OSI public domain test tools and there will soon be comprehensive provision of 3rd party CTS. We therefore recommend a focus during this period on OSI Lower Layers (Public Domain) such as X.25, X.21, X.21bis. Modem testing may also be justified.

However, because of future network development plans it may be more useful in the medium term to start testing of ISDN Basic Access. OTE's testing activities - their scope and relevance - should be reviewed after two years by an independent team appointed by the Commission of experts reporting to the Ministry of Communications.

5.2.5 Interoperability Testing Services

IPPEYS and its labs should comfort users by ensuring responsibility of testing large complex systems in their interoperability aspects.

Perfect knowledge of functional standards and profiles will be needed and for some cases training will be a necessary part of this exercise.

5.2.6 Test Tool/Test Suite Development

The proposed IPPEYS should get involved in development work. IPPEYS should be responsible for formulating the test tool requirements of the public sector as a whole for IT systems. OTE will do the same in the telecommunications sector (5.2.4). IPPEYS will need to have a budget allocated to finance the work defined. However, it should be encouraged (perhaps directed) to subcontract at least half its development work (in the first instance) to private companies. This will form the foundation of the attempt to reproduce in Greece the relationship observed elsewhere in Europe with the difference that the dominant partner will in this case be IPPEYS.

5.2.7 Existing Miscellaneous Areas

In addition to the technical areas recommended above, the following should also be considered:

- electronic payments cards
- digital facsimile
- Greek character sets
- Software quality assurance

The first two meet the criteria of being relatively low cost to develop and produce with prospects of (relatively) many vendors (1st Interim Report). They both have good market prospects (e.g.. sales of facsimile equipment in West Germany over the 12 months ended June 1988 rose over 100 %).

Development work on both has begun relatively recently and so no test services are currently offered elsewhere in Europe. The current developers of the payments card test tool within CTS- 2 are from Spain and Ireland - both 'peripheral' relative to the core EC economies. The new private Greek company should make an early approach to the organizations involved to discuss technology transfer. The Greek retail banking system is in need of modernization and the offer of electronic payments cards could be one component in a strategy of improving customer services.

5.2.8 Complementary Technical Areas

In addition to conformance testing of IT&T systems there are a number of other, complementary areas in which it may be advantageous for Greek involvement. The following list covers the whole range of possible technical fields in which KEPHY may decide to become active. The complementary technical areas for testing are:

- Electro-Magnetic Compatibility
- Electro-Magnetic Interference
- Environmental
- Reliability

The 3rd draft Interim Report outlines the infrastructural requirements for operating test laboratories for each of these areas.

5.2.9 Future Technical Areas

For the second stage (1990-92) of evolution of Greek activities in the IT&T testing domain all of the following are candidate areas:

- RACE and broadband communications protocols
- computer security
- real time testing
- CIM/MAP/TOP
- Computer environments & software
- FDDI

One of the tasks of IPPEYS' Planning department (see below, 5.3.1) during the first stage (1989/90) should be to evaluate these and recommend in which ones Greece should focus its efforts and how that involvement could be developed using the resources of IPPEYS, of the private companies and of OTE.

5.3 Implementation Policy

The following recommendations are concerned with the ways to implement the mechanisms which can bring in success the promotion of CTS in Greece.

A hybrid system considered of public and private initiatives has been considered to be the only conception which can guarantee that the technical recommendations of the study will be effectively implemented.

The public initiative should primarily be concerned with the implementation of the public purchasing policy for IT & T systems and provide support and expert advice to all public organizations concerning OSI. This public body, called IPPEYS, should be endowed with technical expertise in order to permit involvement in development work and to formulate the tool requirements of the public sector as a whole for IT&T systems.

The private sector should be oriented to the emerging business opportunities in this area. However, it has been felt that the idiosyncratic nature of the relevant markets, would not permit fast entrepreneurial actions. Therefore, in the light of the very recent experience from the European Programmes in IT & T (ESPRIT, RACE, BRITE etc.), it is proposed to boost the private initiatives by a call for tenders aiming at the creation of a private company with various participants. This call should be open to Greek and foreign companies, government bodies, OTE, IPPEYS etc. and conform with the technical recommendations of the present study.

5.3.1 Public Sector Involvement

a. IPPEYS

Its fundamental purpose is to implement public purchasing policy for IT&T systems; in conformance with Council Decision 87/95 will provide support and expert advice to all public organizations concerning OSI (not least through the publication of a Greek GOSIP). In particular it will help them define their own informatics requirements, help them prepare Calls for Tender (standard forms and checklists etc.) and evaluate bids (value for money; technical competence). Because of the power that IPPEYS will come to hold over time we strongly recommend that not only should its own performance be annually audited but also that an independent appeals procedure be established whereby firms can challenge their decisions in the event of an unresolvable dispute.

The organizational structure of IPPEYS is presented in the next page.

1. The Planning Section will set the general plan of CTS in Greece. Together with the R&D Section it will evaluate the situation in Europe and abroad and make suggestions on the technical areas and the corresponding laboratories needed, as well as the extent to which the private sector will be involved.
2. The R&D Section has the function of developing the test tools, sometimes also the test suites, the necessary procedures and testing methodology. Its staff of highly qualified engineers follow closely the work on standardization in Europe and international organizations, and are members of their working groups. They thus have state-of-the-art knowledge and, in turn, influence standardization work in IT & T.
3. The Consulting Section will provide consultation and training both to staff members who are performing testing and to other CTS laboratories which wish to set up CT services. An important function of this section is to advise industry on standards and on European and international standardization policy.
4. The Testing Section has the function of carrying out the actual testing according to well specified procedures and using precise methodology. Its staff is required to ensure the proper functioning of the laboratory equipment, which is periodically calibrated.

Organizational Structure of IPPEYS

Recommendations for the CTS staff

It is recommended that the technical director be chosen with technical and managerial meritocracy criteria and be given a mandate of several years. We believe it is of utmost importance that the Technical Director should be independent from the, usually frequent, changes to the Board of Directors. It will not be possible to plan and put into action a program of work if the Technical Director is a political appointee or is directly influenced by the vicissitudes of political change.

We believe it is important that checks and balances be found to guarantee the assessment of the Technical Director and consequently the staff be made only on merit. This is perhaps the most important factor for the success of the whole project and should not be underestimated.

We recommend that the staff participate in the work on Certification and Standardization in European and international organizations and be members of the relevant working groups on standards. This we believe, is the best, and indeed, only way to be informed about the emerging standards which will obviously be the future concern of the laboratory.

The technical activities, infrastructure requirements and running costs are detached in the 3rd Interim Report.

b. ELOT

Upgrade ELOT in personnel and funds in order for it to fulfill its role.

ELOT should be more active in international bodies. That is ELOT should be:

- o Participating - member (P-member) in those ISO/JTC1 Subcommittees with a particular interest (e.g. ISO/JTC1/SC2 for character sets and their coding and ISO/JTC1/SC6, ISO/JTC1/SC21 for OSI).
- o Observer (O-member) in every ISO/JTC1 subcommittee.
- o Participating member in those European WG's that have to do with ODA, FTAM, CSC, Telematic Services and Directors. Also OCR characters and devices.
- o Follow the work of all other EWOS, ETSI and CEN/CLC.WG's.

o TE 48 should be reorganized, in order to be able to follow the work of ISO CEN/CLC, EWOS and ETSI. Working groups of TE 48 should be formed in a "by subject" basis.

c. OTE

To cover the field of telecommunications, OTE should take full responsibility for identifying its needs. It should focus its work on the lower OSI levels (public domain) and terminal equipment. OTE should join the Test House Consortium. Agreement in order to stay up-to-date on European PTT developments in test tool maintenance.

5.3.2 Private Sector Company

The private sector company will be moved from a public call for tenders. This call will specify the technical areas for the activities, the Community participation to the capital and the rules for the action sharing and the management.

The purpose of this call with the support of IMP funds is to motivate the private and public sectors concerned to participate in this venture.

5.4 Certification & Accreditation Scheme

The European Certification and Standardization policies agreed between the CEC, CEN/CENLEC and CEPT must be adopted in Greece as quickly as possible. Implementation of the recently-proposed Greek National Accreditation Scheme is a necessary complement.

5.5 Future & Further Actions

5.5.1 CTS-2bis

It is understood that the CEC will launch another Call for Proposals under the CTS Programme to tackle new domains of conformance testing. This constitutes an excellent opportunity for increasing Greek participation without creating duplication. Both IPPEYS and the recommended private sector company) should be encouraged to respond to the Call.

5.5.2 Publicity & Awareness Campaign

Opinion in government and business circles needs to be sensitized to the commercial importance of Open Systems and standards for IT&T systems. An event should be organized in Greece (possibly with CEC support), early in 1989, to begin this task by targeting senior businessmen and public officials. This event should be the launch of a continuing campaign to raise awareness of the issue throughout the Greek economy. It might also be a platform for announcing the formation of the proposed new private company (assuming that agreements had previously been reached).

5.5.3 Further Techno-Economic Analysis

A 6 month techno-economic study should be funded immediately to define the requirements for a third CTS Programme, or some appropriate equivalent. Taking as its point of departure the findings (and suggested areas for further investigation) of the current study it should investigate the need for integration across CEC Programmes (ESPRIT II, RACE etc.) with regard to objectives and planning of future testing and verification tools domains. The need for both centralized and decentralized co-ordination of developments (as in the USA); the question of the future role of the IT sector as well as the industrial and innovation policy implications and impacts in the context of 1992 all require review.

Technical assistance will be needed in the following:

1. Technical analysis of big users needs e.g. banks, petrol industry, cement industry, ship building.
2. Assistance to implementation of labs Progress reports,
3. Mobilization of private sector to endorse setting up participation
4. Interfacing with IMP Committee.
5. Service training.

5.5.4 Rationalization of Interdependencies with other CEC Programmes

RACE & ESPRIT

Both these large-scale R&D Programmes are now involved in funding the development of verification tools in their respective domains (broadband communications and CIM). There is a need not only for co-ordination and avoidance of duplication with regard to the CTS Programme. There is also the question of the strategic aims behind their activities. The proposed techno-economic study mentioned above would provide input to the definition and coherence of policies and objectives.

STRIDE

Investigate what role this new Programme might play fostering in the less favored regions (including Greece) the complex of innovation processes discussed in the 2nd and 3rd Interim Reports.

SPRINT

As a technology transfer programme of DG XIII-A of the CEC its activities need to be reviewed in the light of the requirements identified in this study and the study recommended above.

5.5.5 European Investment Bank

Venture capital is one means for funding "leap-frogging"-type innovation. However, this kind of financing is poorly understood and not widely practiced in Greece. Action from the EIB specifically focused on promoting private sector exploitation of innovations from and within the peripheral nations of the EC capable of favorably impacting their relative positions in niches of the IT&T sector should be investigated and, if feasible, implemented.

6. GLOSSARY

CCTA	Central Computer & Telecommunications Agency, U.K.
CDC	Commission of the European Community
CEN	Comite Europeen de Normes
CENELEC	Comite Europeen de Normes Electrotechniques
COS	Corporation for Open Systems
CT	Conformance Testing
CTS	Conformance Testing Services
EC	European Community
ELOT	Greek Standards Organisation
ELSYF	Greek Information Systems
FTAM	File Transfer Access & Management
GOSIP	Government OSI Profile
IPPEYS	Institute for Certification
IT&T	Information Technology and Telecommunications
ITSTC	IT Steering Committee responsible for the joint
CEN/CENELEC/CEPT	workprogramme
LAN	Local Area Network
MAP	Manufacturing Automation Protocol
MHS	Message Handling System
NETs	Normes Europeenes de Telecommunications
NIST	National Institute of Standards & Technology
ODA/ODIF	Office Document Architecture/OD Interchange Format
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
PTTs	National Posts, Telegrams & Telecommunications organisations
RACE	Research in Advanced Communications in Europe
RBOCs	Regional Bell Operating Companies
TNC	The Networking Centre, U.K.
TOP	Technical Office Protocol